

Synthesis of 4-Oxo-3-aryl/benzyl-5-alkyl/aryl Thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones*

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In continuation of our previous work¹, syntheses of several new 4-oxo-3-aryl/benzyl-5-alkyl/aryl thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones have been effected.

4-Aryl/benzylthiosemicarbazones, prepared according to the method described previously¹, were condensed with the corresponding α -halo-acids to obtain the title compounds. Table I describes new 4-aryl/benzylthiosemicarbazones and Table II, 4-oxo-3-aryl/benzyl-5-alkyl/aryl thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones.

TABLE I

R'	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		M.P.	Formula	%Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
		A : R = <i>m</i> -tolyl.				B : R = benzyl.		
Ph	162° ^a	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ S	11.7	11.9	134° ^b	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	11.0	11.0
<i>o</i> -HO.C ₆ H ₄	180°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₃ S	11.0	11.2	183°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₃ S	10.0	11.2
<i>p</i> -HO.C ₆ H ₄	165°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₃ S	10.0	11.2	215°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₃ S	11.5	11.2
<i>p</i> -OMe.C ₆ H ₄	162°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	10.6	10.7	156° ^c	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	10.0	10.7
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	204°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.0	10.2	100°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.9	10.2
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH ₂	148°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	10.6	10.8	..	..	..	..
2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	207°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	9.5	9.4	175°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	9.1	9.4
3,4-(OH) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	178°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.0	10.2	105°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.9	10.2
3,4-(OMe)(OH).C ₆ H ₃	215°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.5	10.2	108°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.0	10.2
α -C ₁₀ H ₇	158°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	9.7	10.0	144°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	10.2	10.0

N.B.—(a) Das and Rout, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 68, reprot m.p. 161°.

(b) Tisler, *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, 51, 12016, reports m.p. 136°.

(c) Tisler, *loc. cit.*, reports m.p. 155°.

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1. Trivedi and Shah, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 889; 1964, 41, 704.

TABLE II

R''.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur. Found. Reqd.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur. Found. Reqd.	
A: R=H; R'=m-tolyl.				B: R=H; R'=benzyl.			
Ph	148°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S	10.2 10.4	121°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S	10.5 10.4	
o-HO.C ₆ H ₄	213°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.0 9.8	170°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.7 9.8	
p-HO.C ₆ H ₄	249°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.6 9.8	261°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.1 9.8	
p-OMe.C ₆ H ₄	195°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.2 0.5	168°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.7 9.5	
m-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	163°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	8.7 9.0	171°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	8.8 9.0	
2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	193°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.3 8.5	102°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.7 8.5	
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	145°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.9 9.0	202°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.7 9.0	
3,4-(OMe)(OH).C ₆ H ₃	202°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	8.7 9.0	213°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	8.8 9.0	
α-C ₁₀ H ₇	182°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	8.7 8.9	106°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	8.6 8.9	
C: R=Me; R'=m-tolyl.				D: R=Me; R'=benzyl.			
Ph	116°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	9.7 9.9	102°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	9.6 9.9	
o-HO.C ₆ H ₄	215°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.2 9.4	117°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.6 9.4	
p-HO.C ₆ H ₄	125°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.2 9.4	204°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.5 9.4	
p-OMe.C ₆ H ₄	122°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.8 0.0	145°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.0 9.0	
m-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	165°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ S	8.6 8.7	160°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ S	8.5 8.7	
2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	178°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.3 8.1	141°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	7.9 8.2	
3,4-(OH) ₂ O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	183°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.5 8.7	132°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.0 8.7	
3,4-(OMe)(OH).C ₆ H ₃	165°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.9 8.7	128°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.4 8.7	
α-C ₁₀ H ₇	182°	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	8.3 8.6	104°	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	8.4 8.6	
E: R=Ph; R'=m-tolyl.				F: R=Ph; R'=benzyl.			
Ph	130°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	8.1 8.3	166°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	7.0 8.3	
o-HO.C ₆ H ₄	192°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.8 8.0	160°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.1 8.0	
p-HO.C ₆ H ₄	193°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.8 8.0	220°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.7 8.0	
p-OMe.C ₆ H ₄	177°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.5 7.7	147°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.8 7.7	
m-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	200°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₄ S	7.6 7.4	165°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₄ S	7.2 7.4	
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	228°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ ON ₃ S	7.5 7.8	..	..		
2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	188°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	6.8 7.0	162°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	7.3 7.0	
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	..	..		150°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.9 7.6	
3,4-(OMe)(OH).C ₆ H ₃	185°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.3 7.4	179°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.5 7.4	
α-C ₁₀ H ₇	150°	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ ON ₃ S	7.2 7.4	85°	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ ON ₃ S	7.1 7.4	